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The evolution of biocatalysis: From foundational enzymology to AI-guided biocatalysis through the legacy of Antonio Ballesteros

Manuel Ferrer^a

^aDepartamento de Biocatálisis Aplicada, Instituto de Catalis y Petroleoquímica (ICP), CSIC, Madrid, Spain; ^bPhD program in Biotechnology, University of Barcelona (UB), Barcelona, Spain; ^cDepartment of Life Sciences, Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), Barcelona, Spain; ^dInstitució Catalana de Recerca i Estudis Avançats (ICREA), Barcelona, Spain

ABSTRACT

Over nearly five decades, Antonio Ballesteros helped establish and consolidate biocatalysis at a time when catalysis research was dominated by inorganic chemistry. From early work on enzyme regulation and immobilization to later research on non-conventional media, semisynthetic enzyme stabilization, lipolytic and carbohydrate-active enzymes, metagenomic enzyme discovery and directed evolution, his scientific trajectory closely paralleled the maturation of biocatalysis from fundamental enzymology to an enabling technology for sustainable chemical processes. This commentary uses his career as a framework to trace the conceptual evolution of the field, from controlling individual enzymes to engineering integrated catalytic systems. Beyond specific technological advances, his lasting contribution lies in a platform-oriented vision that connected the enzyme itself, together with its stabilization and optimization, to process design within a coherent strategy. This integrative approach anticipated the current convergence of metagenomics, directed evolution and artificial intelligence (AI)-enabled exploration and the design of enzyme sequence spaces for biocatalysis. As biocatalysis has entered the era of data-driven design, machine learning and circular bioeconomy applications, many of the current challenges, such as navigating vast sequence space, predicting enzyme function, and engineering robust catalysts for industrial deployment, can be seen as extensions of principles he helped articulate decades ago. By revisiting key stages of his scientific trajectory, this commentary also highlights how the major research themes surrounding biocatalysis have evolved over time, from classical enzymology to metagenomic discovery, systems-level biocatalysis and AI-assisted enzyme design. His legacy therefore bridges the foundations of enzymology with the emerging AI-enabled future of biocatalysis.

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1. Enzymatic catalysis and sustainable development goals (SDGs)

Humanity faces the urgent challenge of sustaining social and technological development within planetary boundaries. In response, the United Nations adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015 as a global framework to advance towards a more sustainable, equitable, and resilient future. Achieving many of these goals will require technologies that can decrease environmental impact without compromising economic and social progress. In this context, catalytic processes play a central role by enabling efficient chemical transformations with lower energy demand, reduced environmental impact, and improved resource efficiency.

Enzymatic catalysis (Editorial 2020) is distinctly advantageous because of its high selectivity, ability to operate under mild conditions, and compatibility with renewable feedstocks. Catalysis mediated by natural and engineered enzymes, as well as cell factories, can contribute directly and indirectly to multiple SDGs (Prather 2020). Within the framework of SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), biocatalytic systems support sustainable food production through process improvement, waste reduction, and the valorization of agricultural byproducts. In relation to SDGs 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), enzymatic and microbial catalysis enable the production of advanced biofuels and biobased energy carriers, as well as the conversion of organic waste into biogas and other renewable energy sources.

CONTACT Manuel Ferrer Departamento de Biocatálisis Aplicada, Instituto de Catalis y Petroleoquímica (ICP), CSIC, 28049 Madrid, Spain.

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Biocatalysis also contributes to SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) by supporting the management and valorization of municipal and industrial solid waste. In the context of SDGs 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) and 14 (Life Below Water), biocatalytic systems provide routes for the degradation of persistent pollutants, including synthetic plastics, to foster circular production and consumption models and mitigate environmental contamination. SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) can be addressed through enzymatic and microbial processes applied to wastewater treatment and decontamination. When integrated with bioelectrochemical systems or anaerobic microbial platforms, wastewater treatment can be coupled with sustainable green hydrogen production, simultaneously contributing to SDGs 6, 7, 9, and 13.

In parallel, SDG 13 (Climate Action) benefits from biocatalysis through the development of low-carbon bioprocesses and carbon capture, utilization, and storage strategies that contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. From a socioeconomic perspective, decentralized and cost-effective biocatalytic technologies support SDGs 1 (No Poverty), 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), and 10 (Reduced Inequalities) by facilitating access to clean water, local food processing, and the production of biobased goods. In the fields of health and education, enzymatic catalysis contributes to SDGs 3 (Good Health and Well-being), 4 (Quality Education), and 5 (Gender Equality) through the sustainable production of pharmaceuticals and diagnostic tools, improvements in water quality, and the development of safer and more accessible industrial and laboratory processes. SDGs 15 (Life on Land) and 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions) also benefit from biocatalytic processes, particularly through soil remediation, decreases in the use of hazardous chemicals, and the development of environmentally sustainable technologies. Finally, SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) is intrinsically aligned with biocatalysis, as progress depends on strong collaborations among academia, industry, and policy stakeholders.

The full potential of enzymatic catalysis depends on advances in enzyme discovery, characterization, and engineering (Meissner and Woodley 2022). Global challenges require robust biocatalysts (Prather 2020) that can operate under demanding industrial and environmental conditions, together with strategies to enhance their performance, stability, and functional scope. Despite recent technological advances, efficient methodologies for identifying, characterizing, and deploying optimal biocatalysts, from discovery to application,

remain limited. In this context, the integration of advanced bioinformatics, computational modelling, artificial intelligence (AI), and high-performance computing (HPC) is emerging as a central driver in the evolution of enzymatic catalysis. Modern biocatalysis increasingly relies on the capacity to analyse and integrate large volumes of heterogeneous data, spanning genomic information, protein structures, and functional assays, and to translate this information into mechanistic insight and predictive designs of novel biocatalysts. These approaches (Prather 2020) accelerate the discovery of enzymes and the development of engineered microbial systems, reduce experimental costs, and enable more precise engineering and downstream application strategies.

In this context, the historical evolution of biocatalysis over the past five decades has acquired renewed relevance. The transition from classical enzymology to immobilized systems, from non-conventional media to a new generation of biodegradable polymers that stabilize enzymes using polymerizable deep-eutectic gels, from natural to semisynthetic and fully synthetic enzymes, from carbohydrate biocatalysis to metagenomic discovery and, more recently, to AI-driven enzyme engineering, has not been merely a sequence of technological advances; it has progressively shaped a discipline capable of addressing global sustainability challenges. This trajectory mirrors the scientific journey of Antonio Ballesteros, whose work consistently bridged fundamental enzymology and biocatalysis. Understanding how these foundational developments unfolded is therefore essential to understanding how modern biocatalysis has become a key enabling technology for the SDGs. The following sections examine this evolution in detail, mapping the major phases of the field to the research lines pioneered and advanced under Ballesteros' leadership (Figure 1).

2. Antonio Ballesteros: A life in biocatalysis

A. Ballesteros (1940–2024) was among the pioneers who introduced biocatalysis to the European catalysis community. After training in chemistry and pharmacy, he spent five years in leading laboratories in the USA, UK, Japan and Germany and then created the first biocatalysis group at the Institute of Catalysis and Petrochemistry (within the Spanish National Research Council), in 1969. At that time, the Institute focused on heterogeneous inorganic catalysis, and the idea that enzymes could be treated as true catalysts within the same technological framework was far from obvious. From 1969 onward, A. Ballesteros built a

Figure 1. The evolution of biocatalysis through the legacy of antonio ballesteros. Schematic overview of the main sections of this commentary, using the scientific career of Antonio Ballesteros as a framework to trace the evolution of biocatalysis.

department that eventually grew to approximately 40 researchers, and he took on a series of leadership roles: Spanish delegate to the European Federation of Biotechnology (EFB) Working Parties on Immobilized Biocatalysts and Applied Biocatalysis, chairperson of the EFB Section on Applied Biocatalysis (ESAB), and Executive Editor and later Editor-in-Chief of *Biocatalysis* and *Biotransformation*. These roles placed him at the centre of the European biocatalysis community at the time when immobilized enzymes, nonaqueous biocatalysis, protein engineering, metagenomics and subsequently AI were transforming the field. Throughout his career, his research spanned multiple areas, including studies of the histidine operon, immobilized nucleases, hydrogenases, lipases and saccharide acylation, semi-synthetic enzymes, native, modified and immobilized carbohydrate-active enzymes, prebiotic oligosaccharides *via* glycosidases and glycosyltransferases, enzymes for bioremediation, enzymatic modification of antioxidants, enzymes from metagenomic libraries, and enzymes engineered by directed evolution. These research lines parallel the successive “waves” of modern biocatalysis, spanning the advent of immobilized enzymes in the 1970s, the expansion into nonaqueous media in the 1980s, the consolidation of directed evolution and metagenomics in the 2000s, and the more recent integration of biocatalysis within sustainable chemistry and the bioeconomy. Although A. Ballesteros did not work directly in AI, his emphasis on rigorous

functional characterization, structure–function relationships and integrated enzyme–process optimization laid conceptual foundations that underpin today’s AI-driven biocatalysis. In the following sections, we discuss these phases chronologically, highlighting both the global evolution of biocatalysis and the specific ways in which Ballesteros’ projects and collaborations contributed to and were at the forefront of these trends. These trajectories are summarized in Figure 2, which shows the links between major milestones in modern biocatalysis and the research themes developed by A. Ballesteros across successive decades. The main stages of this evolution, viewed through his scientific trajectory and their relevance to modern biocatalysis, are also summarized in Table 1.

3. Foundations: From operon enzymology to immobilized enzymes

3.1. Early enzymology and regulation

Ballesteros’ scientific career began in heterogeneous catalysis, but he soon shifted towards classical enzymology and metabolic regulation. His early work focused on the enzymes of the histidine operon in *Salmonella typhimurium* (Kovach et al. 1970) and *Escherichia coli* (Tébar et al. 1975), with particular emphasis on ATP phosphoribosyltransferase and the feedback regulation mechanisms that control histidine

Figure 2. Conceptual representation of the evolution of modern biocatalysis over the past five decades. The left side reflects the early phase of molecular enzymology and enzyme control, including regulation, immobilization, and medium engineering. The central area illustrates the expansion of functional diversity through metagenomics and directed evolution, enabling the optimization of catalytic performance and robustness. The right part of the image represents the current AI-enabled era, in which machine learning, structural prediction, and data-driven design allow the predictive navigation of sequence space and rational enzyme engineering. Together, these interconnected layers position biocatalysis as a platform technology for sustainable chemistry, circular bioeconomic processes, renewable energy, and environmentally responsible manufacturing.

Table 1. Evolution of biocatalysis through the scientific trajectory of Antonio Ballesteros.

Stage	Ballesteros' research focus	Key legacy	Modern counterpart
Foundational enzymology	Operon regulation, allostery, artificial enzymes	Rigorous functional understanding of enzymes	AI-supported function prediction grounded in experimental validation
Immobilization and stabilization	Immobilized nucleases, semisynthetic enzymes, sol-gel systems	Enzyme optimization through support and microenvironment engineering	Smart immobilization, hybrid materials, stability-by-design
Expanding catalytic scope	Hydrogenases, lipases, nonaqueous media	Broadening enzyme use beyond classical aqueous hydrolysis	Redox biocatalysis, solvent engineering, synthetic catalysts
Functional products	Carbohydrate-active enzymes, prebiotic oligosaccharides	Controlled synthesis of functional biomolecules	Precision glycobiology, microbiome-oriented nutrition
Biodiversity-driven discovery	Metagenomics, environmental enzymes	Environmental sequence space as a source of innovation	Digital metagenomes, AI-guided mining
Optimization era	Directed evolution, oxidative enzymes	Integration of discovery and engineering	Predictive protein engineering and machine learning
Integrated future	Sustainability-oriented biocatalysis	Platform vision linking enzyme, process, and application	AI-guided, circular, systems-level biocatalysis

biosynthesis. These studies were embedded in broader analyses of bacterial gene regulation and operon control that underpinned the molecular biology revolution of the 1960s and 1970s (Heckmann and Paradisi 2020). This early phase placed him at the centre of fundamental enzymology, spanning kinetics, allosteric regulation, quaternary structure, and the use of spectroscopic and thermodynamic tools to understand enzyme function. Importantly, this deep mechanistic understanding soon evolved into an interest in enzyme

modification and artificial enzyme design, as illustrated by his contribution to the synthesis of flavinyl-papain species as new "artificial" enzymes (Ballesteros et al. 1976), marking an early transition from studying natural regulatory systems to engineering catalytic function.

The significance of this foundational work extends far beyond its historical context. A deep mechanistic understanding of enzyme function remains essential for interpreting metabolic regulation, predicting system-level behaviour, and engineering robust

biocatalysts. Indeed, knowledge of catalytic parameters, conformational dynamics, regulatory mechanisms, and structure–function relationships forms the conceptual backbone upon which modern enzyme discovery, protein engineering, and computational prediction now rest. However, despite decades of biochemical research, substantial gaps in enzyme annotation persist even in well-characterized organisms (Ryu et al. 2019; Barrio-Hernandez et al. 2023; Buton et al. 2023; Rocha et al. 2023; Sanderson et al. 2023; Yu et al. 2023), underscoring how incomplete our understanding of enzyme functions and their contributions to metabolic networks and opening biocatalytic opportunities still are. While contemporary approaches increasingly rely on structural prediction and AI to infer enzymatic activities (Barrio-Hernandez et al. 2023; Abramson et al. 2024), these computational advances continue to depend on rigorous biochemical validation and quantitative functional assays (Yifrach et al. 2018; Cohen et al. 2022). Even in the current era of high-throughput sequencing and AI, reliable progress depends on experimentally grounded insights into how enzymes operate, respond to environmental changes, and integrate within complex metabolic networks. In addition, notable efforts are underway to bridge single-molecule kinetics and molecular diversity with sequence-level information, further strengthening our ability to predict enzyme functions (Kapanidis et al. 2026).

In this sense, Ballesteros' early commitment to rigorous functional characterization anticipated a principle that continues to define the field: transformative advances in biocatalysis ultimately rely on a precise and quantitative understanding of enzyme function.

3.2. Immobilized nucleases and the rise of immobilized biocatalysts

In parallel with the development of industrially relevant immobilized enzymes, for example, L-amino acid acylase processes in Japan in the late 1960s (Lilly 1996), Ballesteros initiated a long-term line of research on immobilized nucleases (Guisan and Ballesteros 1979). From 1974 to 1991, his group studied nucleases immobilized on agarose (Ballesteros et al. 1982) and other supports (Sánchez-Montero et al. 1989), with research spanning their preparation, physicochemical characterization, kinetics under diffusion limitations and application to remove nucleic acids from single-cell protein concentrates (Alcantara et al. 1988). His work addressed the preparation and properties of nucleases immobilized on agarose, the influence of support activation (e.g. cyanogen bromide, and tosylation) and the effect of organic media on activity and stability (Martinez

et al. 1990). Within the broader field, this phase coincided with the consolidation of immobilized enzymes as technical catalysts for continuous processes, the development of carrier-bound and carrier-free systems, and the first systematic frameworks for biocatalyst design considering process constraints. Ballesteros' work is emblematic of this era: it bridged fundamental kinetics and process-oriented characterization, and it did so on the basis of a class of enzymes (nucleases) that were not typical industrial hydrolases but were highly relevant to food and biotechnology applications. Since the early reports on immobilized enzymes (Lilly 1979), the field has undergone a profound transformation. What began as a strategy to enhance operational stability and reuse has evolved into a sophisticated discipline in which immobilization serves as a central tool for biocatalytic process intensification. Immobilization has long been recognized as a key enabling technology for improving enzyme stability, recyclability, and operational robustness in industrial applications (Sheldon and van Pelt 2013).

Contemporary approaches now exploit advanced materials such as covalent organic frameworks to coimmobilize whole cells and enzymes, enabling spatial organization, heightened catalytic efficiency, and improved reusability in integrated systems (Zheng et al. 2024). Additionally, modern strategies extend far beyond simple carrier binding. The integration of nanostructured supports, hybrid materials, and data-driven design, increasingly assisted by AI, now allows fine control over enzyme orientation, the micro-environment, and mass-transfer properties, helping to overcome classical limitations such as diffusional constraints and activity loss (Tadesse and Liu 2025). More recently, innovative immobilization matrices based on deep eutectic systems and eutectic gels have opened new avenues for tailoring the physicochemical micro-environments of biocatalysts (Mercadal et al. 2024). These materials combine solvent and structural functionalities, providing tuneable polarity, viscosity, water activity, and hydrogen-bond networks that can enhance enzyme stability and activity under challenging conditions. In parallel, advances in supramolecular and hybrid materials, including biobased polymers, hierarchical porous supports, and stimuli-responsive matrices, have further expanded the immobilization toolbox. Contributions to the rational design of enzyme–support interactions, including interfacial activation strategies, multipoint covalent attachment, and heterofunctional support, have been instrumental in translating these concepts into robust industrial biocatalysts (Fernandez-Lafuente 2023). Together, these developments illustrate how immobilization has

evolved from a stabilization technique to a platform for engineering enzyme performance through the precise control of structure, environment, and reaction architecture.

Furthermore, the concept of enzyme supramolecular engineering has emerged as a powerful strategy to move beyond conventional immobilization (Giunta et al. 2020). Rather than merely anchoring enzymes onto solid supports, this approach focuses on rationally designing and tuning the nanoenvironment surrounding the biocatalyst to modulate its catalytic behaviour. Engineering synthetic shells and supramolecular matrices around immobilized enzymes can make it possible to control substrate accessibility, local polarity, hydration level, and steric constraints, thereby reshaping catalytic selectivity without altering the protein's primary structure. For instance, the supramolecular tailoring of promiscuous enzymes has demonstrated that careful modification of the surrounding nanostructure can induce enantioselectivity while preserving a broad substrate scope and significantly increasing stability in organic solvents (Giunta et al. 2020). Such strategies illustrate how the nanoenvironment can be engineered as an additional regulatory layer that effectively transforms naturally promiscuous enzymes into customized nanobiocatalysts. In this context, immobilization becomes not merely a stabilization technique but also a platform for functional reprogramming, where materials science, supramolecular chemistry, and protein engineering converge to fine-tune catalytic performance for industrially relevant applications.

In this light, the early work of Ballesteros on immobilized nucleases and diffusion–reaction regimes appears remarkably ahead of its time. His emphasis on understanding transport phenomena, support chemistry, and the relationship between molecular properties and biocatalyst performance anticipated the conceptual framework that underpins today's advanced immobilized biocatalysts. What has changed is not the foundational principle but the level of sophistication: modern immobilization strategies refine and extend ideas that were already central to his scientific vision.

4. Expanding the toolbox: Hydrogenases, lipases and non-conventional media

4.1. Hydrogenases and bioenergetic biocatalysis

Between 1976 and 1990, Ballesteros' group extensively investigated hydrogenases from nitrogen-fixing and nonfixing microorganisms, including *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* (Barate et al. 1987) and *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* (Aparicio et al. 1985). Their studies addressed

fundamental physicochemical and mechanistic aspects such as redox potential, catalytic hydrogen evolution and uptake, oxygen sensitivity, and the thermodynamic constraints that govern biological hydrogen metabolism. During a time when biocatalysis was still largely dominated by hydrolases for synthetic and food-related applications, this focus on hydrogenases represented a deliberate expansion towards redox enzymes and energy-oriented catalysis. Historically, the late 1970s and 1980s marked a transition in the field from viewing enzymes primarily as selective hydrolytic tools to recognizing their potential in electron-transfer and bioenergetic processes. Despite their structural complexity and sensitivity to environmental conditions, hydrogenases represented the potential for biological energy conversion at the molecular level. Ballesteros' work contributed to the emerging understanding that enzymes could participate in processes that were traditionally associated with electrochemistry and inorganic catalysis, thereby broadening the conceptual boundaries of biocatalysis.

At the mechanistic level, hydrogenases are one of the most sophisticated classes of redox enzymes. Three major types are recognized, [FeFe]-, [NiFe]-, and [Fe]-hydrogenases, each differing in active-site architecture, catalytic bias, and oxygen tolerance (Ji et al. 2023). [FeFe]-hydrogenases typically exhibit the highest turnover frequencies for reversible H₂ evolution but are extremely sensitive to oxygen, which limits their operational stability. In contrast, many [NiFe]-hydrogenases are more robust and are frequently biased towards H₂ oxidation, with central roles in microbial energy metabolism. A particularly promising subgroup, [NiFeSe]-hydrogenases, combines relatively high catalytic efficiency with lower product inhibition and partial tolerance to oxygen, making them attractive candidates for sustainable H₂ production. However, the intrinsic sensitivity of most hydrogenases to O₂, along with challenges related to cofactor maturation, electron-transfer coupling, and integration into electrochemical systems, has historically constrained their industrial deployment. Modern strategies aim to overcome these limitations through protein engineering, synthetic maturation pathways, immobilization on conductive materials, and incorporation into bioelectrochemical devices such as microbial electrolysis cells and biofuel cells. These efforts illustrate how the fundamental physicochemical questions addressed in the 1980s, namely, redox potential tuning, catalytic reversibility, thermodynamic efficiency, and environmental sensitivity, remain central to the development of hydrogenase-based technologies for green hydrogen production and bioelectrocatalysis (Ngugi et al. 2014;

Guan et al. 2015; Duarte et al. 2020; Michoud et al. 2021; Purkis et al. 2022).

Although large-scale industrial applications of hydrogenases were limited during that period (Illanes et al. 2018), the scientific insights gained proved foundational for subsequent developments. Hydrogenases now play a central role in research on biological hydrogen production, enzymatic electrocatalysis, biohybrid photoelectrochemical systems, and sustainable energy conversion technologies. Engineered hydrogenases and synthetic biological platforms are being explored for green hydrogen generation, integration into electrode interfaces, and coupling with light-harvesting materials. In this sense, the early mechanistic exploration of hydrogenases anticipated modern efforts to integrate enzymology with renewable energy strategies (Al-Shameri et al. 2023; Ji et al. 2023).

What was once an exploratory line of research has become a pillar of contemporary redox biocatalysis (Ruff et al. 2018; Wei et al. 2018; Cheng et al. 2024; Cai et al. 2025; Filmon et al. 2025), illustrating how basic research on enzyme thermodynamics and electron transfer can shape long-term technological trajectories.

4.2. Lipases, triglycerides and the emergence of enzymes in organic media

From the mid-1980s onward, Ballesteros turned increasingly to lipases as versatile catalysts for both hydrolysis and synthesis. With collaborators such as Francisco J. Plou, he investigated lipases from *Candida rugosa* (Otero et al. 1988), *Penicillium chrysogenum* (Ferrer et al. 2000) and *Thermomyces lanuginosus* (Ferrer et al. 2002), focusing on catalytic behaviour in complex media, surfactant effects, and the synthesis of mono- and diglycerides and other structured lipids, as well as the regioselective acylation of sugars. These efforts were framed within the emerging concept of “biocatalysis in non-conventional media”, including micellar systems, water-in-oil microemulsions and low-water organic environments. At a time when enzymes were still largely associated with aqueous transformations, the demonstration that lipases could retain activity and, in some cases, exhibit enhanced selectivity and stability in such media marked a conceptual turning point for synthetic biocatalysis (Sheldon and Woodley 2018). Historically, this period can be seen as the origin of what has become one of the most industrially dominant enzyme families in biotechnology (Sheldon and Woodley 2018). Today, lipases remain central in both basic research and industrial application. For example, in industrial application and sustainability, lipases are widely used for biodiesel production via

the enzymatic transesterification of triglycerides under mild conditions, a key example of green chemistry replacing harsh chemical catalysis in large-scale processes. They are also applied in the modification of food lipids and the synthesis of enantiopure pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, flavours, nutraceuticals, and biodegradable polymers. The relevance of lipases has not diminished; rather, it has expanded both scientifically and industrially (Tian et al. 2017; Almeida et al. 2021; Reetz 2022; Huang et al. 2023; Chu et al. 2024; Hong and Kortemme 2024; Wang et al. 2025). Accordingly, lipases are increasingly being developed and tailored for circular bioeconomy processes and next-generation green manufacturing (Lozano and García-Verdugo 2023).

Ballesteros' active participation in European research networks and his contributions to reviews on enzymes in non-conventional phases placed him at the centre of this transformation. His work not only described specific industrially relevant processes, including those involving the use of sucrose fatty acid esters (Ferrer et al. 1999) and mono- and dioleoylglycerols (Pastor et al. 1995), but also addressed fundamental questions regarding enzyme adaptation to nonaqueous environments, interfacial activation, and operational robustness. By focusing on both fundamental phenomena and applied outcomes, his research helped establish lipases as model biocatalysts capable of functioning far beyond their natural milieu. A particularly illustrative example was the demonstration that lipase regioselectivity could be modulated simply by adjusting the proportion of cosolvents in two-solvent systems. In a 1999 study, he and his co-workers showed that varying the solvent composition altered the regioselective acylation pattern of sucrose, enabling for the first time the acylation of a secondary hydroxyl group of this highly functionalized sugar with long-chain fatty acids (Ferrer et al. 1999). This finding suggested that relatively small changes in the reaction medium could induce subtle global or active-site conformational adjustments in the enzyme, thereby adjusting the substrate positioning and catalytic outcome without any genetic modification. This work anticipated a concept that has since become central in biocatalysis: that enzyme selectivity, regio-, chemo-, and even enantioselectivity, can be tuned through controlled manipulation of the reaction microenvironment (Liu et al. 2024). Today, the modulation of selectivity through solvent engineering, water activity control, and medium effects is a key strategy in lipase research and industrial biotransformations (Zheng et al. 2025), underscoring the forward-looking nature of these early studies.

What was once achieved empirically, by tuning the solvent composition, water activity, or interfacial

conditions, is now being revisited at a fundamentally different level of resolution. Early observations that subtle changes in the reaction medium could alter regioselectivity (Ferrer et al. 1999) pointed to a deeper principle: catalytic outcomes are governed not only by the primary sequence but also by the geometric and physicochemical organization of the full three-dimensional structure of the enzyme, particularly the active site and its surrounding microenvironment (Lim 2022; Kortemme 2024; Braun et al. 2026). These geometric and physicochemical constraints have now become central design parameters in modern machine learning for biocatalysis research (Q&As 2025). Recent breakthroughs in computational protein design illustrate how far this trajectory has progressed. The classical catalytic triad and oxyanion hole of serine hydrolases, which have long been studied in lipases and esterases, have recently served as templates for the de novo construction of synthetic enzymes with programmable geometry (Lauko et al. 2025). By explicitly modelling active-site preorganization along the reaction coordinate and embedding catalytic motifs into newly generated protein scaffolds, it has become possible to design serine hydrolases with measurable catalytic efficiencies and folds distinct from those of their natural counterparts. These studies highlight that what has changed is not the fundamental logic of catalysis but the scale and precision with which we can interrogate and manipulate it, now allowing the rational construction of synthetic esterase and lipase active sites that support diverse catalytic conversions (Alonso et al. 2020; Roda et al. 2022; Robles-Martín et al. 2023; Muñoz-Tafalla et al. 2025; Vidal et al. 2025; Giménez-Dejóz et al. 2026).

If A. Ballesteros' work anticipated that enzymes could operate beyond aqueous environments and be adapted to industrial contexts through careful control of their surroundings, the current era extends that vision to the molecular and digital domain. The same integrative philosophy, linking fundamental enzymology with technological application, continues to shape modern biocatalysis in an approach that is now enriched by AI, structural design, and systems-level engineering. In this sense, the trajectory from solvent-engineered lipases to AI-guided catalytic architectures is not a rupture with the past but the natural continuation of a conceptual framework he helped establish.

5. Stabilization, semisynthetic enzymes and sol-gel biocatalysts

A recurring theme throughout Ballesteros' scientific career, developed in close and sustained collaboration

with Francisco J. Plou, was the stabilization and functional enhancement of enzymes through chemical and material-based strategies. From 1989 to 2006, the preparation of semisynthetic enzymes constituted a central research line in his group. This effort translated into numerous studies on the chemical modification of hydrolases, including the acylation and PEGylation of subtilisin and lipases, to improve activity, thermostability, and operational robustness, particularly under demanding conditions such as the presence of surfactants or organic solvents (Calvo et al. 1995). In parallel, Ballesteros explored sol-gel encapsulation and enzyme-polymer nanocomposites, embedding enzymes within silicate or hybrid matrices to generate highly stable biocatalysts (Gill and Ballesteros 1998). The edited volume *Stability and Stabilization of Biocatalysts* (Elsevier 1998) (Ballesteros et al. 1998) consolidated both conceptual and practical aspects of enzyme stabilization and became a reference framework for subsequent developments in the field.

Historically, this work coincided with the rise of protein engineering through directed evolution and rational mutagenesis, as exemplified by the pioneering studies of Willem Stemmer and Frances H. Arnold (Arnold 2018). They demonstrated that enzymes can be adapted through directed evolution and protein engineering to operate in nonaqueous environments and perform new catalytic functions. Whereas the dominant paradigm that followed emphasized genetic diversification and selection, Ballesteros pursued a complementary route: tailoring enzyme performance through chemical modification and materials science. His semisynthetic enzymes and sol-gel biocatalysts anticipated the idea that enzyme function can be tuned not only at the sequence level but also through controlled modification of the protein surface and microenvironment (Gill and Ballesteros 1998).

The relevance of these strategies has become even more evident in recent years. Contemporary biocatalysis increasingly relies on hybrid approaches that combine protein engineering with chemical and material-based stabilization. Modern examples include enzyme-polymer conjugates designed for enhanced solvent tolerance, nanostructured encapsulation systems for continuous-flow catalysis (Zheng et al. 2024), and silica-based biohybrid materials that protect enzymes under extreme pH, temperature or oxidative conditions (Giunta et al. 2020; Foroutan Kalourazi et al. 2024). Similarly, enzyme immobilization within sol-gel-derived matrices has re-emerged in the context of biosensors, electrocatalytic interfaces and environmental remediation technologies (Maghraby et al. 2023). PEGylation and other covalent modifications are now

widely used not only in industrial enzymes but also in therapeutic proteins to improve their half-life and resistance to denaturation (Bento et al. 2024).

In this landscape, the conceptual foundation laid by Ballesteros, the idea that enzyme performance can be rationally improved through chemical modification and engineered microenvironments, appears strikingly contemporary. Stabilization techniques that were once considered auxiliary are now recognized as integral components of multilevel enzyme optimization, complementing AI-guided sequence design and advanced protein engineering. Thus, Ballesteros' work on semi-synthetic enzymes and sol-gel biocatalysts represents not only a historical phase of stabilization research but also an early articulation of a systems-level view of enzyme optimization, one that integrates chemistry, materials science and enzymology to expand the operational boundaries of biocatalysis.

6. Carbohydrate-active enzymes and prebiotic oligosaccharides

Since biocatalysis offered regio- and stereoselective routes to these complex carbohydrates under mild conditions, and immobilization enabled continuous processes and high space-time yields (Illanes et al. 2018), from 1994 onward, Ballesteros and his collaborator Francisco J. Plou explicitly identified native, modified and immobilized enzymes acting on carbohydrates and the production of prebiotic additives using glycosidases and glycosyltransferases as central research lines. During this period, his group developed an integrated program spanning structural enzymology, chemical modification, immobilization strategies, and process development. Major contributions included (i) structure-function studies and chemical modification of cyclodextrin glucanotransferases (CGTases) and dextransucrases, including controlled shifts in product profiles from cyclodextrins towards maltooligosaccharides (Martín et al. 2004); (ii) immobilization of CGTases and dextransucrases for the synthesis of maltooligosyl and methyl polyglucosides, as well as nutritionally relevant glucooligosaccharides; (iii) coordinated projects on the enzymatic production of first- and second-generation prebiotic oligosaccharides using glucosyltransferases and fructosyltransferases (Álvaro-Benito et al. 2007; Fernández-Arrojo et al. 2007); and (iv) advanced studies on fructosyltransferases and the incorporation of prebiotic oligosaccharides into nutrition, including *in vitro* evaluation of prebiotic activity (Rodríguez-Colinas et al. 2014; Gonzalez-Alfonso et al. 2018).

At the field level, this research coincided with the rapid expansion of functional foods and nutraceuticals

(Granato et al. 2010), developments that continue to play a central role in modern society through microbiome-oriented nutrition and health interventions (Sanders et al. 2019; Armet et al. 2022; Ross et al. 2024). Importantly, the relevance of carbohydrate-active enzymes has not diminished; rather, it has expanded significantly. The enzymatic synthesis of prebiotic oligosaccharides has become a cornerstone of the global functional ingredient market, particularly in infant nutrition, microbiome-targeted foods, and medical nutrition, where structurally defined glycans are increasingly valued for their specificity and physiological effects (Samara et al. 2022).

Beyond classical prebiotic synthesis, current research is increasingly focused on enzymatic strategies to remodel carbohydrate profiles directly within food matrices. Instead of merely adding prebiotic fibres, enzymes such as fructosyltransferases, levansucrases and transglycosidases are being explored to convert intrinsic sucrose and simple sugars into higher-molecular-weight, partially or nondigestible carbohydrates. This approach simultaneously reduces the free sugar content and increases functional fibre, thereby improving the glycemic response and metabolic impact without altering ingredient labels (Durães et al. 2023). Such strategies are particularly relevant in processed fruit products and infant foods, as the mechanical processing in the manufacture of these products disrupts the plant matrix, increases sugar bioavailability, and reduces effective fibre content. Enzymatic transglycosylation offers a biocatalytic route to redirect carbon flux from rapidly absorbable sugars towards fructans, glucans or resistant starch structures, contributing to improved glycemic control and microbiota modulation.

Thus, Ballesteros' approach to carbohydrate-active enzymes was not limited to process optimization but was rooted in a clear conceptual objective: the controlled enzymatic synthesis of structurally defined oligosaccharides with tailored functional properties (Santos-Moriano et al. 2019). At a time when the functional food sector was still consolidating its scientific basis, his work emphasized that the biological activity of prebiotic carbohydrates depends critically on the linkage type, degree of polymerization, and fine structural features. By integrating enzyme specificity, product profile modulation, and scalable immobilized systems, his group sought not only to produce oligosaccharides but also to control their architecture with precision. This perspective anticipates the current emphasis on structure-function relationships in prebiotic science, where defined glycans are being increasingly designed to modulate specific microbial populations and metabolic pathways (Tolonen et al.

2022). In the context of growing interest in functional nutrition and microbiome-targeted interventions and mounting evidence that different microorganisms metabolize distinct glycans and thereby influence host health (Dridi et al. 2023), the ability to enzymatically synthesize complex carbohydrates with precise structural fidelity has become increasingly central (Liu and Fang 2025). In this sense, Ballesteros' work laid early conceptual groundwork for linking glycoscience, enzymology, and the emerging field of health-oriented food innovation.

7. Metagenomics: From environmental DNA to industrial biocatalysts

In the early 2000s, biocatalysis entered the “metagenomic era”, in which enzymes were discovered directly from environmental DNA without the need to culture the producing organisms (Fernández-Arrojo et al. 2010). This transition from enzyme-centered discovery to the exploration of environmental functional diversity is summarized in Figure 3. Ballesteros was an early adopter of this strategy for the screening of metagenomes from harsh environments and animal microbiomes (e.g. bovine rumen and earthworm gut) for new hydrolases, esterases, laccases and other enzymes with unique structural features and high robustness in organic solvents or extreme conditions (Reyes-Duarte et al. 2005; Belouqui et al. 2006; Ferrer et al. 2007).

These efforts were among the first to demonstrate the now widely recognized impact of metagenomics on biocatalysis, significantly expanding the accessible sequence space and facilitating the discovery of enzymes with unprecedented stability, selectivity, and substrate scope (Hogg et al. 2024). Beyond their direct contributions to future biocatalyst development, these studies have drawn the attention of the biotechnology community to the active pursuit of environmental biocatalysis (Hogg et al. 2024), ranging from enzymatic remediation to novel green processes (Alcalde et al. 2006).

Importantly, these studies anticipated the transformative role that metagenomics now plays in biocatalysis. By accessing the vast reservoir of uncultured microbial diversity, they demonstrated that environmental DNA could serve not merely as a source of novelty but also as a strategic platform for discovering enzymes preadapted to extreme physicochemical conditions and unconventional substrates. This foresight laid the conceptual groundwork for current approaches that combine metagenomic mining with high-throughput screening, structure-guided engineering, and AI to accelerate enzyme discovery and optimization (e.g. Hogg et al. 2024).

Metagenomics is no longer viewed as exploratory but as a cornerstone technology in industrial biocatalysis, enabling the systematic exploration of functional “dark matter” (Ferrer et al. 2019) and the development

Figure 3. The microbiome nexus. The microbiome links human, animal, and environmental systems, enabling innovative solutions in health, sustainability, and biotechnology.

of robust catalysts for sustainable chemical processes (Santos et al. 2025). At a time when metagenomics was still largely perceived as a biodiversity tool (Alcalde et al. 2006), these contributions reframed it as a driver of functional innovation in chemistry, anticipating its later integration with directed evolution, protein engineering, synthetic biology, and data-driven enzyme discovery strategies.

Beyond its initial role as a source of novel hydrolases and oxidoreductases, including nitrilases, carboxylesterases, laccases and α/β -hydrolase-type lipases, metagenomics rapidly evolved into a strategic engine for expanding the functional boundaries of biocatalysis (Hogg et al. 2024). The systematic mining of environmental sequence space enabled the discovery of entire enzyme panels tailored for synthetically relevant transformations, particularly those involved in C=X bond reduction, such as reductive aminases (RedAms), monoamine oxidases (MAO-Ns), amine dehydrogenases (AmdHs), imine reductases (IREDs), ene-reductases, transaminases (ω -TAs), ketoreductases (KREDs) and alcohol dehydrogenases (ADHs). Large metagenomic IRED libraries comprising hundreds of homologs demonstrated the existence of enzymes with broad substrate scope and unexpected catalytic promiscuity, including enzymes capable of both reductive amination and C=C bond reduction. Similarly, metagenome-derived transaminases and KREDs showed enhanced tolerance to high concentrations of amine donors, organic solvents and sterically demanding substrates, whereas obtaining such tolerance often requires extensive engineering when starting from conventional scaffolds. In parallel, the metagenomic exploration of extreme and contaminated environments yielded robust oxidative and functionalization enzymes, including cytochrome P450 monooxygenases (both classical and self-sufficient variants), FAD-dependent monooxygenases, halogenases, and epoxide hydrolases (EHs), including limonene epoxide hydrolases (LEHs) and α/β -epoxide hydrolases (Hogg et al. 2024). These enzymes frequently display intrinsic thermostability, solvent resistance, or unusual regio- and stereoselectivity that can directly address longstanding industrial constraints. Particularly illustrative is the identification of plastic-degrading enzymes such as poly(ethylene terephthalate) hydrolases (PETases), as well as enzymes involved in the degradation of polyurethanes and polyamides, discovered through environmental metagenome mining and subsequently optimized through protein engineering for circular bioeconomic applications (Ahituv et al. 2025; Seo et al. 2025). Together, these examples demonstrate that metagenomics has affected virtually all major catalytic classes relevant to

modern biocatalysis, hydrolases, oxidoreductases, transferases and lyases by providing evolutionarily pre-adapted scaffolds that reduce the necessary mutational burden during directed evolution campaigns. Although far from being restricted to exploratory biodiversity studies, metagenomics has become a cornerstone methodology for enzyme discovery, functional diversification and industrial innovation (Hogg et al. 2024).

Crucially, the field itself has undergone a methodological transformation (Hogg et al. 2024), from the classical functional screening of environmental DNA libraries to the computational mining of digital metagenomes, sequence similarity networks, high-throughput microfluidic screening, and AI-assisted prioritization of candidates. What began as biodiversity-driven exploration has matured into an integrated, data-intensive platform in which metagenomic diversity, structural modelling, and machine learning converge to rationally navigate vast sequence spaces (Figure 4). In this context, metagenomics no longer represents merely a discovery tool but a foundational layer upon which modern biocatalysis, combining diversity generation, predictive design, and evolutionary refinement, is constructed.

However, beyond the technological capacity to screen faster and sequence more deeply, a fundamental challenge remains: identifying the enzymes that best fit a specific biocatalytic process requires not only diversity but also contextualized understanding. The robust meta-analysis of large-scale omics data sets is essential for obtaining a logical and system-level overview of microbial metabolism (Cervantes-Gracias et al. 2022), and its interpretation can be substantially enhanced through machine learning-based analytical frameworks (Cho et al. 2023). The integration of big data analytics with functional metagenomics enables the informed prioritization of candidate enzymes and biosynthesis-related gene cluster regions, facilitating rational and evidence-based biomolecule selection strategies (Bell et al. 2021).

In parallel, AI protein language models (pLMs) have emerged as powerful learners of the contextual “vocabulary” that defines proteins through their sequence, structure and function (Thumuluri et al. 2022b; Lin et al. 2023). These models not only improve functional annotation but also increasingly enable the design of novel proteins that exhibit expression efficiencies approaching those of natural enzymes and enhanced resistance to mutational perturbation (Ebert and Pelletier 2017; Kamble et al. 2019). Particularly relevant for extremophile research, specialized pLM “dialects” are being developed to capture sequence signatures

Figure 4. Translating microbiome knowledge into solutions. Overview of the microbiome innovation chain, integrating data-driven insights, computational analysis, system optimization, and translation into functional biotechnological and biomedical solutions.

associated with adaptations to pH and salinity extremes (Amalgendina et al. 2024). When combined with highly accurate structural prediction methods (Jumper et al. 2021) and computational frameworks capable of analysing ligand binding, catalytic performance and stability parameters (Xiang et al. 2022), these approaches offer the potential to decipher the habitat-dependent molecular “dialects” of extremophilic proteins, an area that remains only partially understood beyond genomic feature-level analyses (Arias et al. 2023). Only by integrating contextualized meta-omics analysis, advanced machine learning, structural prediction, and ultrahigh-throughput functional validation will it be possible to guarantee the systematic identification of enzymes optimally suited to defined biocatalytic processes. This convergence marks the transition from empirical discovery to predictive, context-aware enzyme design, representing the next frontier in metagenomic biocatalysis.

An additional and often underappreciated challenge concerns the sustainable, ethical and legally compliant exploration of genetic diversity, particularly in view of its ultimate transfer into industrial biocatalytic processes. The ability to translate biodiversity into scalable and economically viable biocatalysts requires not only technological innovation but also responsible sampling strategies, regulatory clarity, and long-term preservation frameworks that ensure reproducibility,

accessibility and benefit sharing. Without a structured approach to governance, metadata standardization and legal compliance, the transition from environmental discovery to industrial deployment may become constrained by regulatory uncertainty or loss of traceability. Therefore, sustainable biodiscovery must be conceived from the outset as part of an integrated pipeline that links environmental exploration, functional validation, data stewardship and industrial translation. Indeed, the discovery, preservation and responsible exploitation of biodiversity require specialized equipment, advanced sampling design, and logistical infrastructures that can support extended expeditions under environmentally sensitive conditions (Lallier et al. 2014; Rotter et al. 2021). Such efforts should incorporate low-carbon transportation strategies and autonomous sampling and preprocessing capabilities to ensure operational independence during long campaigns. Equally critical is the design of statistically robust sampling strategies that balance sampled volumes, depth gradients, and spatial and temporal replication to ensure analytical validity. Moreover, sampling approaches may differ substantially depending on whether the objective is broad biodiversity assessment or targeted biodiscovery of biotechnologically relevant cultivable microorganisms. Environmental responsibility must also extend to the collection, transport, preservation and long-term storage of

microorganisms containing even yet unknown biocatalytic potential, whose viability is essential for future functional characterization and biotechnological exploitation (Rotter et al. 2021). These activities must operate within established governance frameworks, including strict adherence to the Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS), as well as relevant provisions of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and emerging regulations concerning biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction (BBNJ). The ongoing policy debate surrounding digital sequence information (DSI) further underscores the importance of clear legal interpretation and equitable benefit-sharing mechanisms. To ensure continuity and prevent the duplication of effort or loss of valuable biodiversity data after funding cycles conclude, the field should prioritize the establishment of long-term inventories of environmental voucher samples accompanied by standardized protocols and FAIR-compliant metadata infrastructures. Open-access repositories and interoperable data platforms can safeguard accessibility, facilitate collaboration, and promote future capitalization on results. Experience gained through large-scale exploration initiatives has demonstrated the importance of coordinated governance frameworks and expert guidance in navigating evolving legal landscapes related to novel sampling technologies, cultivation methodologies, and DSI regulation (Lallier et al. 2014; Rotter et al. 2021).

In this landscape, the early efforts of Ballesteros to explore enzymatic diversity directly from environmental sources anticipated the modern view that nature's uncultured microbial communities represent a vast reservoir of catalytic innovation. What began as the experimental exploration of environmental biocatalysts has evolved into a data-driven discipline that integrates metagenomic mining, ultrahigh-throughput screening and machine learning-guided enzyme discovery.

8. Directed evolution in biocatalysis: From empirical optimization to AI-guided engineering

Beyond its role as a methodological complement to metagenomic discovery, directed evolution has progressively addressed several longstanding cornerstones of biocatalysis. Historically, major bottlenecks limiting the broader industrial deployment of enzymes included insufficient stability under process conditions, limited substrate scope, poor activity towards nonnatural substrates, suboptimal expression in heterologous hosts, and incompatibility with organic solvents or elevated

temperatures. Over the past two decades, iterative cycles of mutagenesis and screening have systematically overcome many of these constraints, transforming fragile biological catalysts into robust industrial tools (Wang et al. 2021; Hossack et al. 2023). In particular, directed evolution has enabled (i) dramatic improvements in thermostability and solvent tolerance; (ii) the expansion of substrate promiscuity towards synthetic intermediates; (iii) the inversion or enhancement of enantioselectivity; (iv) the adaptation of enzymes to nonnatural cofactors or reaction environments; and (v) the optimization of expression and folding in industrial hosts. These advances underpin the transition of biocatalysis from niche applications to a central technology in pharmaceutical and fine chemical synthesis (Buller et al. 2023).

Within this broader transformation, Ballesteros' contributions must be understood not merely as isolated engineering efforts but as part of the consolidation of protein engineering as a strategic pillar of applied biocatalysis. Through collaborations with Miguel Alcalde and others, his group applied directed evolution to enzymes including, for example, laccases, peroxygenases and Rubisco variants, increasing catalytic efficiency, stability and operational robustness under industrially relevant conditions (Torres-Salas et al. 2013; Gomez-Fernandez et al. 2018; Molina-Espeja et al. 2019). These studies addressed precisely the types of limitations that historically constrained oxidative enzymes in applied settings, including low stability, restricted substrate range, and incompatibility with process conditions, thereby contributing to the maturation of enzymatic catalysis beyond laboratory-scale feasibility.

The field has since entered a new phase in which directed evolution itself is being reshaped by AI. One of the central challenges of classical directed evolution lies in the combinatorial explosion of mutational space and the high experimental burden required to identify beneficial mutations. Recent machine-learning-guided workflows have demonstrated that sequence-function landscapes can be modelled to prioritize mutations, reduce library size, and accelerate convergence towards high-performance variants (e.g. Tsuboyama et al. 2023; Yu et al. 2023; Landwehr et al. 2025). Data-driven approaches can now guide combinatorial library design, predict synergistic mutations, and enable the semirational navigation of vast mutational landscapes. Moreover, the emergence of AI-based pLMs (Thumuluri et al. 2022a) and structure prediction platforms (Jumper et al. 2021) has begun to bridge the gap between random mutagenesis and predictive engineering. Rather than relying exclusively on empirical

screening, contemporary workflows increasingly integrate structural modelling, evolutionary conservation analysis, and machine learning-based fitness prediction. As highlighted in recent reviews (Wang et al. 2021; Hossack et al. 2023), this convergence marks a shift from exploration towards guided evolution.

Despite these advances, significant challenges remain. Enzyme engineering for complex, multistep cascades, tolerance to industrial impurity streams, long-term operational stability, scalability, and regulatory compatibility continues to demand innovation. Furthermore, understanding epistatic interactions and higher-order mutational effects remains a central unresolved problem in protein evolution. The integration of AI does not eliminate experimental validation but rather reframes it within a predictive, data-informed context. In this light, Ballesteros' early integration of enzyme discovery and enzyme optimization anticipated a paradigm that has now become mainstream: the convergence of biodiversity mining, directed evolution, and computational prediction. While he did not primarily develop new methodological platforms in directed evolution, his strategic adoption and application of these approaches helped to bridge enzyme discovery and functional optimization at a time when their integration was far from routine. His work thus aligns with the broader transformation of directed evolution into a cornerstone technology of modern chemistry, an evolution of the field that culminated symbolically in the 2018 Nobel Prize awarded to Frances H. Arnold (Arnold 2018).

9. Late career: Biocatalysis within the emerging European bioeconomy

In the last phase of his career, Ballesteros continued to work on immobilized enzymes, prebiotic oligosaccharides and antioxidant derivatives, often in the context of continuous processes and industrially relevant reactors. For example, his work includes packed-bed reactors with immobilized β -galactosidase for continuous galactooligosaccharides (GOS) production (Füreder et al. 2020) and the enzymatic production of fully deacetylated chitooligosaccharides (Santos-Moriano et al. 2019) with neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory properties, as well as the enzymatic modification of flavonoles by combining glucosylation and acylation (Gonzalez-Alfonso et al. 2024; Rodríguez-García et al. 2025). These studies exemplify a mature form of biocatalysis that characterized by route design, reactor integration and an orientation towards health and sustainability. They also support the contemporary perspective that biocatalysis

is a central process in sustainable chemistry, as enzymes are characterized by low E-factors, high selectivity and compatibility with renewable feedstocks. Moreover, Ballesteros remained active in research related to lignocellulosic materials (Kunamneni et al. 2007), prebiotics (Füreder et al. 2020) and the enzymatic valorization of agroresidues (Neifar et al. 2020), contributing to the broader bioeconomic agenda that links biocatalysis with the circular use of biomass and waste streams.

This late-career orientation towards biomass transformation and the upgrading of complex substrates into high-value products unfolded in parallel with the evolution of European research and innovation frameworks. From the Sixth and Seventh Framework Programmes (FP6, 2002–2006; FP7, 2007–2013), in which industrial biotechnology and sustainable processing began to gain structured prominence, to Horizon 2020 (2014–2020), which consolidated the concepts of the knowledge-based bioeconomy and circular economy, European funding progressively shifted from discipline-driven research towards mission-oriented innovation addressing societal challenges. Under Horizon 2020, biotechnology, resource efficiency, and the valorization of biomass were explicitly framed within “Societal Challenge 2” (Food security, sustainable agriculture and the bioeconomy) and later reinforced through public–private partnerships such as the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU). This trajectory has continued under Horizon Europe (2021–2027), where clusters dedicated to “Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment” explicitly promote the circular use of biological resources, waste stream valorization, and low-carbon industrial transformation in alignment with the European Green Deal.

The increasing emphasis on sustainability metrics, life-cycle thinking, carbon neutrality, and industrial scalability mirrors the progressive maturation of Ballesteros' research agenda, from enzyme discovery and immobilization strategies to integrated bioprocesses for renewable feedstocks and functional biomolecules. In this sense, his scientific evolution was not merely contemporaneous with changing funding landscapes; instead, it embodied the transition of European biotechnology from foundational enzymology towards systemic bioeconomic integration. The focus on lignocellulosic biomass, agroresidue valorization, functional oligosaccharides, and continuous reactor systems reflects precisely the priorities that came to define EU bioeconomy policy: coupling scientific excellence with industrial relevance, sustainability, and circularity.

10. Integrated technologies in modern biocatalysis

No single technological approach is sufficient to create the next generation of efficient biocatalysts. Instead, progress in the field increasingly relies on the integration of complementary strategies, including protein engineering, enzyme immobilization, metagenomics, computational prediction, machine learning, and systems-level biochemical analysis. This technological convergence is transforming the way enzymes are discovered, designed, and implemented in industrial processes. Protein engineering and immobilization strategies for the improvement of industrial enzymes can, when used in combination, lead to 10–100-fold increases in catalytic activity and operational stability while enabling enzyme reuse over multiple reaction cycles (often >10–20 cycles). In addition, the engineered biocatalysts used in pharmaceutical synthesis frequently achieve enantioselectivities above 99% ee and high product yields, highlighting their advantages over traditional chemical catalysis in terms of selectivity, process efficiency, and sustainability (Farhan et al. 2025). Recent advances also reflect the growing integration of computational and data-driven approaches with experimental biocatalysis. The increasing computational power available for predicting the functions of uncharacterized enzymes (Yu et al. 2023), combined with the integration of biochemical data, reaction modelling, and metabolic pathway optimization, is accelerating enzyme discovery and enabling the emergence of predictive biocatalysis (Tripathi et al. 2025). Moreover, advances in enzyme engineering, metagenomics, and machine learning are expanding the diversity of available catalysts beyond the limits of naturally occurring metabolism. In particular, significant efforts are now focused on expanding the catalytic repertoire of enzymes by enabling new-to-nature transformations such as carbene and nitrene transfer reactions (e.g. C–H functionalization, cyclopropanation, and aziridination), abiotic bond-forming reactions such as C–Si, C–B, and C–C couplings, and selective radical transformations that do not occur in natural metabolisms. These developments illustrate the emergence of artificial and engineered biocatalysis, where multiple technological platforms converge to design new catalytic functions (Markus et al. 2023). The convergence of enzyme repurposing, *de novo* enzyme design, and AI is therefore redefining the field, enabling the creation of catalysts that extend beyond natural metabolic capabilities and opening new opportunities for sustainable chemical synthesis (Fasan 2025).

From this perspective, many of these developments build upon the integrative vision advocated by Ballesteros decades ago. His work consistently emphasized that advances in biocatalysis would emerge not from isolated technological breakthroughs but from the coordinated application of complementary approaches spanning enzymology, molecular biology, process engineering, and environmental exploration. What has changed today is the scale and sophistication of the available tools, from AI-driven protein design to metagenomic mining and ultrahigh-throughput experimentation, but the underlying principle remains the same: the most powerful innovations in biocatalysis arise from the convergence of disciplines and technologies. In this context, modern integrated biocatalysis can be viewed as the technological maturation of a strategy that Ballesteros helped to articulate early on.

11. A legacy bridging foundations and future frontiers in biocatalysis

Over five decades, the evolution of biocatalysis, from single immobilized enzymes to metagenomic libraries, protein engineering and AI-assisted enzyme design and AI-assisted biocatalysis, traces a set of interconnected trajectories that closely mirror Ballesteros' scientific journey. His early work on operon regulation and enzyme allostery evolved naturally into a sustained effort to control and improve enzyme performance: first through immobilization and chemical modification and later through directed evolution and metagenomic discovery. What began as fundamental enzymology progressively expanded into an integrated vision of catalytic systems. The transition from simple carrier-bound enzymes to advanced sol–gel biocomposites and enzyme–polymer nanomaterials anticipated a broader shift towards engineered catalytic materials tailored for specific process environments. Likewise, the exploration of enzymes in micelles, microemulsions and organic solvents expanded the operational landscape of biocatalysis beyond aqueous systems, thereby increasing the accessible chemical space and reinforcing the idea that catalytic performance depends not only on sequence but also on context. Over time, his research moved from specialty chemical synthesis towards applications aligned with nutrition, health, environmental remediation and continuous processing, areas that have become increasingly central to the circular bioeconomy.

Ballesteros' legacy therefore extends beyond specific enzymes or technologies. It is fundamentally

conceptual: a vision of biocatalysis that integrates molecular understanding with industrial application and mechanistic enzymology with societal responsibility. His “platform view”, linking enzyme discovery, chemical modification, immobilization, and enzyme and process optimization, anticipated what is now recognized as a multilayer optimization paradigm in industrial biocatalysis. Contemporary state-of-the-art approaches treat enzyme sequence engineering, catalytic mechanism, substrate context, reactor configuration, life-cycle metrics and functionality as interconnected variables rather than isolated parameters. A particularly striking transformation, unimaginable at the beginning of Ballesteros’ career, is the integration of machine learning and AI into nearly every layer of the biocatalysis workflow. Predictive models are now used to estimate enzyme activity, stability and selectivity; guide mutagenesis strategies; design focused libraries; optimize reaction conditions; and even propose multienzyme cascades. High-throughput experimentation combined with machine learning enables the exploration of sequence–function relationships at previously inaccessible scales, effectively turning parts of enzyme discovery and optimization into data-driven search problems. In parallel, the AI-assisted navigation of the metagenomic sequence space links protein diversity directly to chemical reactivity, accelerating the identification of catalysts for defined synthetic targets.

In this sense, the current era of data- and AI-driven biocatalysis does not depart from his scientific vision of enzymes as true catalysts but rather fulfils it at a new level of scale and sophistication. The future of biocatalysis will continue to depend, as it did throughout his career, on combining the curiosity-driven exploration of enzyme function with the rigorous engineering of catalysts, processes and sustainable systems capable of addressing global challenges. His legacy lies precisely in having helped build the conceptual foundations upon which that future now stands.

12. A career spanning an era of scientific and global transformation

When A. Ballesteros published his first scientific paper in 1967, the landscape of enzymology and biotechnology was profoundly different from that today. By 1971, fewer than 1770 enzymes had been characterized and formally classified (Enzyme Nomenclature 1978), the Enzyme Commission (EC) system was still in its infancy, no complete genome had yet been sequenced, and only 7 structures had been deposited in the newly founded Protein Data Bank (PDB) (Heckmann and

Paradisi 2020). Biocatalysis was limited to a small number of industrial processes (Arbige and Pitcher 1989; Lilly 1996, Heckmann and Paradisi 2020), mainly in food and bulk chemistry, and enzymes were still regarded by many chemists as fragile biological curiosities rather than robust industrial catalysts; thus, by the late 1970s, the world market for industrial enzymes was approximately US\$300 million in sales value (O’Sullivan 1981). Over the course of his career, the scale of biological knowledge expanded exponentially. Today, more than 250 million protein sequences are publicly available (Rives et al. 2021), more than 112,000 individual enzymes from thousands of organisms have been cataloged in the BRENDA database (Hauenstein et al. 2026), with 8,698 distinct enzyme classes (EC numbers); 249,906 experimental structures have been deposited in the Protein Data Bank (PDB Consortium 2026); and hundreds of millions of additional structures can be computationally predicted (Fleming et al. 2025). Entire microbial communities can be interrogated through metagenomics, and enzyme discovery has shifted from organism-by-organism exploration to the systematic mining of global sequence space. What was once the study of individual catalytic systems became the navigation of an immense functional universe.

During the same period, the global context within which science operates has changed dramatically. In 1967, atmospheric CO₂ concentrations were approximately 322 ppm; today, they exceed 420 ppm. Interestingly, A. Ballesteros often anticipated the importance of biological solutions to carbon management well before these topics became central in biotechnology and catalysis. He maintained constant engagement with the scientific literature and frequently emphasized in internal discussions the potential relevance of enzymes involved in CO₂ fixation and carbon recycling. Today, such catalytic systems have become key components of modern biocatalysis and sustainable biotechnology (Bierbaumer et al. 2023), highlighting once again his capacity to recognize emerging scientific directions at an early stage. Additionally, the global mean surface temperature has increased by approximately one degree Celsius over that period, and climate change, resource depletion and environmental degradation have become the defining challenges of our era (IPCC 2023). In parallel, biocatalysis has evolved from a niche discipline into a cornerstone of sustainable chemistry: thousands of industrial biocatalytic processes are now implemented across pharmaceuticals, fine chemicals, food, biofuels and materials, and enzymes are recognized as key enabling technologies for low-carbon manufacturing and circular bioeconomic strategies. The global

industrial enzymes market, a subset of the broader enzyme market, was valued at approximately \$9.1 billion in 2026 and is projected to reach \$14.3 billion by 2032, reflecting a CAGR of 6.9% (Research and Markets 2026). This aligns with estimates from the broader enzymes market, which, including pharmaceutical and diagnostic applications, was valued at \$14.9 billion in 2025 and is expected to grow at a similar rate (Enzymes Market 2026–2032). Within this landscape, industrial enzymes (e.g. carbohydrases and proteases) represent the largest segment, accounting for more than 56% of the total enzyme market because of their indispensable roles in detergents, food processing, animal feed, and biofuels.

13. Role of AI and high-performance computing in biocatalysis

A. Ballesteros continued his research into the period when biocatalysis began to enter the era of AI and high-performance computing. Today, machine learning, protein language models, structural prediction, and

large-scale molecular simulations are enabling the exploration of vast enzyme sequence space, enzyme engineering and the predictive design of improved biocatalysts. Clearly, simulations have changed from a mechanistic analysis technique to a hypothesis generation technique; the unprecedented pace of AI innovation makes us wonder what is next.

Many highly disruptive AI tools are now in use in biocatalysis research. Cofolding deep learning techniques have facilitated accurate structural determination, which is a key prerequisite for designing variants, bioprospecting enzymes for specific substrates, and so on. In a recent study, for example, we engineered bacterial proteins with surgical precision, conferring novel biochemical properties on the bacterial strain (Vidal et al. 2025). Such a study would have never been possible without a tool like AlphaFold. Although the folding problem remains, from an inverse approach, we encounter another disruptive technique, ProteinMPNN (Dauparas et al. 2022). This AI code (along with similar ones) uses a deep learning-based graph neural network to predict the “best” set of amino acids at each

Figure 5. aMLProt: An automated machine learning framework that supports enzyme discovery and engineering for biocatalysis. Conceptual overview of the aMLProt framework integrating protein sequence features and embeddings from pretrained protein language models with multiple machine learning algorithms. The platform enables the automated construction of predictive models to support enzyme discovery, functional prediction and the optimization of catalytic properties that are relevant to biocatalytic applications.

position for a given backbone structure. It is currently used in many computational engineering efforts, especially when a significant number of mutations are introduced to achieve more stable variants, and often leads to better expression (Sumida et al. 2024). Combining the above techniques with diffusion methods, which can be used to generate novel backbones, forms one of the basic protocols for the design of completely *de novo* proteins (Kim et al. 2026).

In parallel, generative modelling and transformers (PLMs) have been used to generate *de novo* enzymes. Designs are often improved through active learning procedures, where classical molecular modelling or bioinformatic techniques are used to enrich and filter predictions (Diaz-Rovira et al. 2025).

The use of language model embedding has revolutionized the scientific field, and biocatalysis is not an exception. We have already introduced its potential for generating *de novo* proteins and enzymes. ZymCTRL from the Ferruz laboratory, for example, can generate active enzymes with sequence identities below 40% compared with natural proteins. Moreover, fine-tuning of the initial model made it possible to obtain activities comparable to those of their natural counterparts (Munsamy et al. 2024). Tailoring those models for predicting biocatalysis properties, however, is slightly more challenging: everything depends on the data. Optimal pH predictors, for example, are trained on tens of thousands of data points and function well for classification but still cannot accurately predict mutations (Gado et al. 2025); being able to predict how a mutation might affect biocatalysis properties relies on data generation.

The lack of extensive data often requires the use of simpler machine learning techniques, such as support vector machines and ridge or random forest classifiers. The approach here involves more work, filtering data, defining descriptors and building models. These techniques have now been used for several years, preceding the era of multimodal language models (see, for example, a recent review on this journey by Shi et al. 2026). To facilitate the construction of these models, aMLProt is being implemented as an automated framework for building machine learning models in enzyme engineering and bioprospecting, integrating 19 classifiers and 26 regressors along with pretrained protein language models (see Figure 5).

Overall, AI techniques currently provide accurate classification models and structure generation, which can lead to fast and efficient bioprospecting or *de novo* enzyme-encoding generation. Fine-tuning stability also seems to be largely accomplished by AI models. For more specific properties, it might still be

necessary to generate specific data sets or to combine AI methods with alternative techniques such as molecular modelling.

14. Concluding remarks

Biocatalysis was originally built on experimental facts, with enzyme discovery and optimization depending on labour-intensive screening, biochemical characterization, and empirical observation. A. Ballesteros was part of that formative experimental era, but his integrative view of enzyme function, stabilization, and application anticipated the logic of modern biocatalysis. Today, the field is shifting towards prediction: high-throughput sequencing at unprecedented scale, together with standardized sequencing and data-sharing pipelines, has made us extraordinarily effective at digitizing microbial life. However, realizing the full potential of this transformation requires more than sequence accumulation alone. Microbiomes must be understood and organized as contextualized resources, integrating environmental metadata, community composition, functional roles, ecological dynamics, and adaptive strategies, ideally within interoperable collections and infrastructures that preserve both biological material and digital information. In this new landscape, such data-driven frameworks are increasingly enabling the rational design of stabilized enzyme variants, the *de novo* generation of enzyme scaffolds, and the expansion of catalytic repertoires towards new-to-nature reactions. These advances lay the foundations for a truly predictive biocatalysis, capable of accelerating development timelines and responding to the growing demands of industry, while simultaneously addressing broader socio-economic and environmental challenges associated with sustainability, resource efficiency, and the reduction of environmental impact.

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Authors' contribution

CRedit: **Manuel Ferrer**: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **Patricia Molina-Espeja**: Investigation, Project administration, Writing

– review & editing; **Laura Fernandez-Lopez**: Investigation, Writing – review & editing; **Víctor Guallar**: Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft; **Rafael Bargiela**: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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ORCID

Manuel Ferrer <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-4962-4714>
 Patricia Molina-Espeja <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-2590-0932>
 Laura Fernandez-Lopez <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-8861-3191>
 Rubén Muñoz-Tafalla <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-4380-4888>
 Víctor Guallar <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4580-1114>
 Rafael Bargiela <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1442-3269>

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